

Aedes albopictus Larval DNA Extraction for F1534S KDR Mutation in the Voltage-Gated Na⁺ Channels

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Abstract

In medical entomology, some species of mosquitoes are closely examined because they are significant biological vectors of several devastating diseases. Among the 900 species that encompass the *Aedes* genus, the *A. aegypti* and *A. albopictus* are of a particular concern in the United States because these invasive species can spread dangerous diseases (such yellow fever and dengue fever) to vulnerable, naïve populations. In addition, mosquitoes can develop resistance to chemical control through genetic mutations that modify the target site of the insecticides, decrease their absorption, or improve their capacity for chemical detoxification. This research focuses to investigate if there is the presence of the F1534S, a type of knock-down resistance (KDR) mutation in the voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSC) which is a protein on the mosquitoes' neurons. This mutation in the mosquito's nervous system confers resistance to pyrethroid insecticides, commonly used for mosquito control in the U.S.. To detect KDR mutations, this study used DNA extracted from wild *Aedes albopictus* as the template for the VGSC polymerase chain reaction. Therefore, the aim of this research is to assess the prevalence of this mutation in Wake County, which is important for developing efficient vector control methods. Moreover, the findings from this research hold significant implications for

mosquito control programs in North Carolina and in the rest of the country, as well as other aspects related to population dynamics and species distribution.

Introduction

Among many species of *Aedes spp.*, two species, *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*, are concerning vectors for diseases in the United States, with *Aedes aegypti* considered the primary vector and *Aedes albopictus* the secondary (Reed et al., 2018). Among the diseases these mosquitoes transmit are Dengue virus (break-bone fever), Yellow fever, Chikungunya virus, Zika virus, West Nile virus, Eastern equine encephalitis virus, and La Crosse virus (the primary cause of pediatric encephalitis in the U.S.) (Abernathy et al., 2022). Although there has been no record of *Aedes aegypti* in North Carolina, the species has been found in Washington D.C. and coastal South Carolina (Lima et al., 2016). In contrast, *Aedes albopictus* has a high prevalence in North Carolina (Reed et al., 2018). In addition, *Aedes albopictus* is considered one of the world's most dangerous invasive species (Lee et al., 2022). The female sucks blood from mammals, especially humans, in order to have nutrients to lay her eggs (Lee et al., 2022). Besides the major epidemiological factor, these mosquitoes are known for being truculent biters which is alarming to the population inhabiting the areas where they are present (Abernathy et al., 2022). North Carolina has several different approaches in controlling mosquito surveillance, because the state manages it at either regional, county, or municipal levels and is located under public works, health agencies, or other environmental service agencies (Del Rosario et al., 2014). The average yearly budget of North Carolina's mosquito

control programs, including salaries, chemicals, and equipment, is typically small, being \$66,303 in 2009 (Del Rosario et al., 2014) and \$36,373–\$741,377 in 2023 (Stroops et al., 2023).

Chemical insecticides are commonly used for mosquito control. Pyrethroids are a class of chemical insecticides such as permethrin, deltamethrin, and bifenthrin that have an effect on mosquitoes known as knock-down, causing paralysis and death. With that in mind, this research aims to look for a mutation of the gene encoding the voltage-gated sodium channel (VGSC), a protein responsible for synapses to occur within the nervous systems. Pyrethroids target the VGSC, and mutations in that protein can result in knock-down resistance (KDR) therefore interfering with electrical signals in the nervous system (Chen et al., 2016). This study aims to find the F1534S in wild *Aedes albopictus* in Wake County since the mutations have been found there (Abernathy et al., 2022). Among the many mutations conferring KDR, three have been well studied: at codon 1534 in domain 3 that has phenylalanine instead of serine, cysteine, or leucine; at codon 1532 threonine is substituted with isoleucine and at 1016 glycine is substituted with valine (Abernathy et al., 2022). The current study will focus on detecting the F1534S KDR mutation in eggs from wild caught mosquitoes using polymerase chain reaction on larval specimens after hatching these mosquitoes' eggs. This is important because KDR is correlated with the overuse of pyrethroids since it is most common and cost-effective insecticide in the U.S. for the past twenty years. This observational study was conducted throughout three Wake Technical Community College campuses to examine the prevalence of the F1534S mutation in Wake County.

Material and Methods

Mosquito Collections

Mosquito's eggs were collected on two different Wake Technical Community college campuses. Although only mosquito eggs of *Aedes albopictus* were collected, four CDC Miniature Light Trap Model 512 were set up on three campuses (Figure 1) in the attempt to collect adults. Hence, no adult *Aedes albopictus* were collected. Mosquito egg traps were also put out and constitute of black plastic cups, germination paper stuck to the border of the cup, and ~350 ml of water in each cup. Germination paper is used for the *Aedes* mosquitoes to stick their eggs on. Therefore, germination paper is used in ovitraps to collect the eggs because it mimics natural breeding environments, due to its exceptional water absorption and retention qualities, which make egg collecting and counting simple. It also offers a reliable and stable surface for egg laying. Approximately ten to fifteen cups were placed at each time on the area wished to collect eggs for three days. In addition, these cups were placed approximately five to ten meters apart since *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* display a behavior called skip-oviposition behavior, which is a preference to lay eggs in when there are multiple cups available. They lay 40% more eggs in one cup than in others (Reinbold-Wasson et al., 2021). Thus, this would allow for different females to lay their eggs in different cups, creating more chances of finding the mutation on a larger number of mosquitoes. After collecting the eggs, they were hatched in white trays filled with water, one tray for each collection site. The germination paper along with TetraMin Tropical Flakes Fish Food were put inside the trays for seven days, approximately, until larvae were identified. Since fish food contains vital nutrients that encourage the growth of microorganisms and algae, which serve as food for mosquito

larvae, simulating natural conditions and supporting their development, hatching the mosquito eggs. The choice of TetraMin as the source of nutrition is due to reduced conductivity, pH, ammonium and phosphate concentrations. Additionally, TetraMin diet results in the biggest body sizes and calorie intakes of adult mosquitoes (Müller et al., 2013).

Figure 1. Map with the locations of all three campuses where the ovitraps and light traps were displayed. (Map generated by

<https://mapmaker.nationalgeographic.org/map/05ee0056dfa242a59da98ecab197f777/edit>)

Location A: Southern Campus, 9101 Fayetteville Rd, Raleigh, NC 27603

Location B: Beltline Education Center, 3200 Bush St, Raleigh, NC 27609

Location C: Scott Northern Wake Campus, 6600 Louisburg Rd, Raleigh, NC 27616

DNA Extraction

After separating the larvae into specimens one through seven (Table 2), a sterile blue mini pestle was used to thoroughly grind each sample, containing the number of larvae indicated in the table 1. Without removing the pestle, 500 μL of extraction buffer (200 mM Tris, pH 7.5, 250 mM NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, 0.5% SDS) was added to the sample, and the pestle was used to continue to grind the sample. After removing the pestle, the tube was vortexed for five seconds, then centrifuged for three minutes at maximum speed. A 200 μL pipettor was used to transfer 150 μL of the supernatant twice to a new microcentrifuge tube, and 300 μL of isopropanol was then added to the tube with the DNA. With the lid closed, the tube was inverted 3-4 times to mix, and then the tube sat at room temperature for two minutes. The tube was centrifuged at full speed for five minutes. Most of the isopropanol was dumped into a waste container without disturbing the pellet and 300 μL of 70% ethanol was added. The tube lid was closed, and the tube inverted two to three times. The tube was centrifuged for one minute and most of the ethanol was removed. The tube was centrifuged at full speed for five to 10 seconds to bring all the remaining ethanol to the bottom. A 20 μL micropipette was used to remove the last few microliters of solution, avoiding the pellet. The tube was left open and after any residual ethanol evaporated 25 μL of TE buffer (10 mM Tris, pH 8, 1 mM EDTA) was added to the tube to dissolve the DNA pellet. The tube was left at room temperature for two minutes to allow the DNA to rehydrate.

Table 1. Summary of *Aedes albopictus* eggs collected, hatched, and larval DNA extraction from different locations and dates.

Locations		Date (Collection)	Number of ovitraps	Eggs	Hatching Date	Total Larvae	Larvae	Extraction Date
Location A	Creek	9/6/23	15	25	10/6/23	9	Specimen 1: 5 larvae Specimen 2: 4 larvae	10/11/23
	Creek	10/4/23	5	69	10/11/23	8	Specimen 4: 4 larvae Specimen 5: 4 larvae	10/18/23
Location C	Pond	9/9/23	4	23	10/6/23	2	Specimen 3: 2 larvae	10/11/23
	Forest	9/9/23	2	40	10/11/23	11	Specimen 6: 5 larvae Specimen 7: 6 larvae	10/18/23

PCR and Sequencing

PCR was conducted to amplify the desired region. In previous research, the primers V3F and V3R were used to amplify the domain 3 of the VGSC (Abernathy et al., 2022) (Bowman et al. 2022). The Primer concentration (23 μ L) was added to a PCR bead and allowed the bead to dissolve for 1 minute and then 2 μ L of DNA was added directly to this mix. Afterwards, the samples were placed in a thermal cycler for 35 cycles of the following profile: Denaturing step: 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 seconds; annealing step: 58 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 seconds; extending step: 72 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 seconds; and final extension step: 72 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes.

Table 2. Primer sequences that were utilized to amplify *Aedes albopictus*'s voltage-gated sodium channel genes in domain 3.

Primer	Sequence
V3F(domain 3)	GAG AAC TCG CCG ATG AAC TT
V3R(domain 3)	TAG CTT TCA GCG GCT TCT TC

The PCR products were visualized using gel electrophoresis as previously described by the Biology Instructors of Wake Technical Community College, 2023. Briefly, aliquots (5 μ L) of each PCR reaction were mixed with loading dye and loaded into the wells of a 2% agarose gel and electrophoresed at 120 V for 30 minutes. A DNA ladder was simultaneously electrophoresed as a size reference (Biology Instructors of Wake Technical Community College, 2023).

Results

Mosquito Control:

Due to limited adult collection, this research was only able to extract DNA from the mosquitoes' larvae. Two hundred and fifty-nine eggs were collected from ovitraps on locations A and C. In these locations, the light traps did not collect any adult *Aedes albopictus*. Neither adults nor eggs of *Aedes albopictus* were collected in the location B from the four ovitraps and four light traps set on campus. Only adult *Culex pipiens* were collected in all 4 light traps. Since *C. pipiens* deposit their eggs on the surface of the water rather than on germination paper, no eggs from this species were retrieved (Kauffman et. al. 2017).

PCR and Sequencing Results

Gel electrophoresis indicated the presence of bands of approximately the size 300 to 400 base pairs, indicating successful amplification of VGSC in specimens one, two, three, five, six, and seven (Figure 2). These PCR samples were then sent to Genewiz for sequencing, but the results were inconclusive, due to lack of priming with the primer used.

Figure 2. PCR gel electrophoresis shows the glowing bands of the samples one, two, three, five, six, and seven that have DNA and that were copied from the primer used.

Discussion

In the past, the F1534S KDR mutation has been found in Wake County in adult *Aedes albopictus* (Abernathy et al., 2022). Controlling these mosquitoes is crucial for public health, as they are biological vectors for many diseases. Knowing the prevalence of the F1534S mutation helps North Carolina combat this invasive species. With climate change, the number of mosquitoes, especially *Aedes albopictus*, is increasing drastically (Ryan et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, mosquitoes can be controlled through biological and chemical methods.

Some natural insecticidal *Aedes spp.* control methods can be a large number of aquatic organisms including fish, like the *Gambusia affinis*, amphibians, copepods, odonate young instars, water bugs, and even larvae of other mosquito species (Benelli et al., 2016). On top of that, bats also eat mosquitoes and reside in North Carolina. *Myotis lucifugus*, most known as Little Brown Bat is an example. While mosquitoes are a part of *Myotis lucifugus*'s diet, they are not its primary prey (Gonsalves et al. 2013). In addition, the Germacrene D-4-ol, an essential oil derived from fresh leaves of *Zanthoxylum monophyllum*, not only demonstrated efficacy in combating *Aedes spp.* larvae but also showed no harm to *Gambusia affinis* (Pavela &

Govindarajan, 2017). In contrast, some chemical control methods are currently used in mosquito control. For example, permethrin which is a synthetic chemical widely used as an insecticide, acaricide, and insect repellent. Permethrin-impregnated clothes, such as the uniforms used by the U.S. military personnel, act as insecticide to protect soldiers. This use of Permethrin is one of the possible explanations of the reason no KDR mutation was found in a study done in Fort Liberty in comparison with Wake County, due to these uniforms reducing landings and preventing bites, therefore repelling and killing the mosquitoes (Abernathy et al., 2022). Therefore, there is a need to find other environmentally safe methods to combat the population of *Aedes* without leading to the selection of mutants, addressing alternative methods for the use of pyrethroids that effectively controls mosquitoes with minimal environmental impact.

In the current research, there were some limitations in obtaining adult *A. albopictus*. The weather at the time the traps were set out is one of the potential limitations. Both location A and C had rain on the period the traps were active. Location A had 0.1 inch of rain expected in the twenty-four-hour period and 0.9 inch on location C. Additionally, there were winds at locations A and C of eight and four miles per hour, respectively. In addition, the batteries on the traps only lasted for approximately 48 hours while conducting the experiment, leaving a short window to collect the adults. Equally important, the absence of eggs on location B might be due to both light traps and ovitraps being displayed next to the interstate 440, a busy highway, since *Aedes. spp* has a preference on crossing calm and small roads over busy and large highways (Regilme et al., 2021). Nevertheless, there is a strong correlation between *Aedes* preferring to lay their eggs in household containers (Kraemer et al., 2015). Also,

limitations have occurred when sequencing the samples to search for the mutation. In molecular biology, the primers M13 forward (M13F): TGAAAACGACGGCCAGT and reverse (M13R): CAGGAAACAGCTATGAC are often used for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification and DNA sequencing. In other words, these primers position themselves on each side of the desired DNA segment, enabling amplification or sequencing of that specific region. The M13 sequence was attached to our primers by Genewiz for sequencing. Moreover, the lack of proper sequencing could be a problem with our primers or it could have been a problem with their primers. They used the M13 to try to sequence so it might not have sequenced properly because of that. Besides, since the PCR gel showed the glowing bands of 300 to 400 base pairs, it means that the samples with DNA replicated from our primer as indicated by the light bands. Therefore, even though the DNA samples bound to the primers, a full sequencing would be needed in order to look at the sequence to confirm the mutation.

Research must more thoroughly assess the mutation rates among *Ae. albopictus* throughout North Carolina and identify the underlying mechanisms of resistance selection. Also, further studies should gauge the aspects on how the weather impacts adult's distribution, and how long traps should be placed in each location in order to collect the mosquitoes. Understanding these phenomena is crucial as the identification of wild mutants becomes essential for public health. In addition, the increase in resistant mosquito populations will make it harder to manage these vectors, which will eventually cause a rise in illnesses carried by mosquitoes. Thus, it is imperative that public organizations take a proactive and comprehensive strategy to reduce this growing threat in order to protect the public health.

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Literature cited

Abernathy, H. A., Hollingsworth, B. D., Giandomenico, D. A., Moser, K. A., Juliano, J. J., Bowman,

N. M., . . . Boyce, R. M. (2022). Prevalence of knock-down resistance F1534S mutations in *Aedes albopictus* (skuse) (diptera: Culicidae) in North Carolina. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 59(4), 1363–1367. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jme/tjac054>

Benelli, G., Jeffries, C.L., & Walker, T. (2016). Biological Control of Mosquito Vectors: Past, Present, and Future. *Insects* 2016, 7(4), 52. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects7040052>

Biology Instructors of Wake Technical Community College. (2023). *General Biology II:*

Laboratory Manual (last edited October 2023). Wake Technical Community College.

Bowman N. M., Akialis K., Cave G., Barrera R., Apperson C. S., et al. (2018) Pyrethroid

insecticides maintain repellent effect on knock-down resistant populations of *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes. *PLOS ONE* 13(5), e0196410.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196410>

- Chen, H., Li, K., Wang, X., Yang, X., Lin, Y., Cai, F., . . . Ma, Y. (2016). First identification of kdr allele F1534S in VGSC gene and its association with resistance to pyrethroid insecticides in *Aedes albopictus* populations from Haikou city, Hainan Island, China. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 5(31), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-016-0125-x>
- Del Rosario, K. L., Richards, S. L., Anderson, A. L., & Balanay, J. A. (2014). Current status of mosquito control programs in North Carolina: The need for cost-effectiveness analysis. *Journal of Environmental Health*, 76, 8–15.
- Gonsalves, L., Bicknell, B., Law, B., Webb, C., & Monamy, V. (2013). Mosquito consumption by insectivorous bats: Does size matter? *PLOS ONE*, 8(10), e77183. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0077183>
- Kauffman, E., Payne, A., Franke, M. A., Schmid, M. A., Harris, E., & Kramer, L. D. (2017). Rearing of *Culex* spp. and *Aedes* spp. mosquitoes. *Bio-protocol*, 7(17), e2542. <https://doi.org/10.21769/BioProtoc.2542>
- Kraemer, M. U., Sinka, M. E., Duda, K. A., Mylne, A. Q., Shearer, F. M., Barker, C. M., Moore, C. G., Carvalho, R. G., Coelho, G. E., Van Bortel, W., Hendrickx, G., Schaffner, F., Elyazar, I. R., Teng, H. J., Brady, O. J., Messina, J. P., Pigott, D. M., Scott, T. W., Smith, D. L., Wint, G. R., . . . Hay, S. I. (2015). The global distribution of the arbovirus vectors *Aedes aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus*. *eLife*, 4. Article e08347. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.08347>

- Lee, I. H., & Duvall, L. B. (2022). Maternally instigated diapause in *Aedes albopictus*: Coordinating experience and internal state for survival in variable environments. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, *16*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2022.778264>
- Lima, A., Lovin, D. D., Hickner, P. V., & Severson, D. W. (2016). Evidence for an overwintering population of *Aedes aegypti* in Capitol Hill neighborhood, Washington, DC. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, *94*(1), 231–235. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.15-0351>
- Müller, R., Knautz, T., Völker, J., Kress, A., Kuch, U., & Oehlmann, J. (2013). Appropriate larval food quality and quantity for *Aedes albopictus* (Diptera: Culicidae). *Journal of Medical Entomology*, *50*(3), 668–673. <https://doi.org/10.1603/me12094>
- Pavela, R., & Govindarajan, M. (2017). The essential oil from *Zanthoxylum monophyllum* a potential mosquito larvicide with low toxicity to the non-target fish *Gambusia affinis*. *Journal of Pest Science*, *90*(1), 369-378. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-016-0763-6>
- Reed, E. M. X., Byrd, B. D., Richards, S. L., Eckardt, M., Williams, C., & Reiskind, M. H. (2019). A statewide survey of container mosquitoes (diptera: Culicidae) in North Carolina, 2016: A multiagency surveillance response to zika using ovitraps. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, *56*(2), 483–490. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jme/tjy190>
- Reinbold-Wasson, D., & Michael, H. R. (2021). Comparative skip-oviposition behavior among container breeding *Aedes* spp. mosquitoes (diptera: Culicidae). *Journal of Medical Entomology*, *58*(6), 2091–2100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jme/tjab084>

Regilme, M. A. F., Carvajal, T. M., Honnen, A. C., Amalin, D. M., & Watanabe, K. (2021). The influence of roads on the fine-scale population genetic structure of the dengue vector *Aedes aegypti* (Linnaeus). *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, *15*(2), Article e0009139. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009139>

Ryan S. J., Carlson C. J., Mordecai E. A., & Johnson L. R. (2019). Global expansion and redistribution of Aedes-borne virus transmission risk with climate change. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, *13*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0007213>

Stoops, C. A., Qualls, W. A., Nguyen, T. T., & Richards, S. L. (2019). A review of studies evaluating insecticide barrier treatments for mosquito control from 1944 to 2018. *Environmental Health Insights*, *13*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178630219859004>